

THE MAGIC OF

VISITING HUESCA

Sanctuary of Nuestra Señora de Lourdes

Tourist attractions

- Main tourist attractions
- Hermitage
- Church
- Museum
- Monument
- Rocafort
- Tourist attractions
- Point of interest
- Interpretation centre
- Historical site

- Natural Protected Areas
- Sobrarbe Geopark Boundary
- Other routes
- Reservoirs and lagoons
- Rivers
- County boundary
- Region boundary
- Roads
- Road names

- ### Topography
- > 1800 m
 - 600 m - 1800 m
 - < 600 m

Population centres

- Huesca** County capital
 - Zaidín** Municipality
- Total population
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Sources of information:
Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN)
Diputación Provincial de Huesca (DPH)
Infraestructura de Datos Espaciales de Aragón (IDEARAGON)

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Tourist trails

- GR 1
- GR 11
- GR 15
- GR 17
- GR 65
- C. N. Hoyas de Huesca
- Ways of Saint James

